

MONITORING AND CONTROL OF MANUFACTURING PROCESSES

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada onlayn ishlov berishni optimallashtirish usullarini muhokama qilinadi, bu esa jarayon samaradorligini, asboblarning xizmat muddatini va mahsulot sifatini yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Unda an'anaviy va takomillashtirilgan monitoring va boshqaruv texnikalari taqqoslanadi, usullar, arxitekturalar va jihozlar o'rtasidagi farqlar baholanadi. Hozirgi va kelajakdagi tizimlarning tizimli tahlili ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarida adaptiv boshqaruvni joriy etishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Adaptiv; Boshqaruv; Monitoring; Ishlab chiqarish jarayonlari.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются методы оптимизации онлайн-обработки с помощью адаптивного управления, что способствует улучшению эффективности процесса, срока службы инструментов и качества продукции. Сравниваются традиционные и улучшенные методы мониторинга и управления, оцениваются различия в методах, архитектуре и оборудовании. Системный анализ современных и будущих систем фокусируется на внедрении адаптивного управления в производственные процессы.

Ключевые слова: Адаптивный; Управление; Мониторинг; Производственные процессы.

Abstract. This paper discusses methods for optimizing online processing through adaptive control, improving process efficiency, tooling life, and product quality. It compares conventional and enhanced monitoring and control techniques, evaluating differences in methods, architectures, and equipment. A systematic analysis of current and future systems focuses on the implementation of adaptive control in manufacturing processes.

Keywords: Adaptive; Control; Monitoring; Manufacturing processes.

Introduction. There are several reasons for installing a monitoring system in manufacturing processes. Modern equipment must be flexible, sustainable, and operate

with minimal human intervention, while machine tools should work without errors. Two major issues in metal cutting are tool wear and breakage, leading to frequent downtimes. Tool breakage is a significant cause of unscheduled stoppages, costing both time and capital [1]. Studies suggest that downtime due to cutter breakage ranges from 6.8% to 20% on average. Current manufacturing trends call for higher machining speeds, reduced tool wear, and less reliance on machining fluids to increase productivity and enable "more with less" production [2]. Sustainability is also a key factor, as rising energy costs and environmental concerns push manufacturing enterprises to reduce energy consumption. Monitoring and control of manufacturing processes have become essential for the development and sustainability of the industry. Process monitoring involves analyzing sensor data (e.g., force, vision, temperature) to determine process states. Operators perform tasks such as detecting missing or broken tools and identifying chatter sounds. Automated monitoring algorithms use filtered sensor data, along with operator input, to assess process conditions. Process control involves adjusting variables like feed, speed, and depth-of-cut to regulate processes. Operators make real-time adjustments to suppress issues like chatter, respond to tool breakage, or modify part programs to optimize the process.

Adaptive Control (AC) has been introduced as a method of optimizing machining variables on-line, during the process. AC has been classified [3] into 3 main categories:

- ACC Adaptive Control with Constraints
- ACO Adaptive Control with Optimization
- GAC Geometry Adaptive Control

Typically, ACC systems are used in roughing operations to maximize material removal by maintaining high cutting forces, preventing tool breakage.

ACO systems optimize machine settings to improve performance indices like production time and unit cost. They typically adjust cutting variables to maximize material removal rate while considering constraints like surface roughness, power consumption, cutting forces, machining time, and cost.

GAC systems focus on optimizing processes to maintain product quality, such as dimensional accuracy and surface finish. They are typically used in finishing operations to ensure consistent part quality despite tool wear and structural deflections.

This study reviews research on manufacturing process monitoring and control, examines their impact on industry applications, and discusses current research directions.

Fig. 1: Process – Monitor – Control Loop

Sensors and sensing devices

The techniques for the monitoring of machining have been traditionally categorized into two methods:

- Direct
- Indirect

Direct monitoring methods offer high accuracy but are limited by practical constraints, making them more suited for laboratory use. In contrast, indirect methods are less accurate but more practical for machine shop applications, measuring auxiliary quantities and correlating them with machining phenomena.

Direct methods require vision systems, but factors like illumination and cutting fluids can interfere, making them unstable in production environments. However, laser sensor-based systems have been developed to evaluate tool wear by measuring displacement and light intensity [4]. These methods can accurately measure flank wear greater than 40 μm . Additionally, CCD cameras can capture tool images during machining. Using image acquisition and creating a database of tools under extreme conditions, an algorithm for further data processing can be developed.

Conclusion. Monitoring and control of manufacturing processes are key drivers of development and sustainability in the industry. AC systems enhance the controllability and reliability of machining processes. Though introduced in the 1960s, AC has not yet fully matured for widespread industrial use. This paper reviews recent research on monitoring systems, decision-making systems, and AC systems. As the demand for quality, efficiency, and sustainability grows due to environmental concerns and regulations, implementing AC in production lines for online optimization—beyond just tool conditioning—is increasingly vital for more efficient and sustainable manufacturing.

Adabiyotlar

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